

TOWARD A POSTCOLONIAL CONFLICTOLOGY

RETHINKING THE RIFFIAN STRUGGLE

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*“Together we shall engrave on the cornerstones of our houses the collective memory of our beloved Rif, with clear letters: ‘Watch out! For us, **dignity is non-negotiable.**’”*

Hirak-leader Nasser Zefzafi¹

“We must dare to invent the future.”

Thomas Sankara (1985)²

¹ Own translation from Akarkach (2018, p. 7): “*Gezamenlijk zullen we op de hoekstenen van onze huizen het collectief geheugen van onze geliefde Rif graveren. Met duidelijke letters: ‘Pas op! Voor ons is de waardigheid niet onderhandelbaar.’*”

² Retrieved from Katihabwa (2009).

ABSTRACT

This thesis develops a novel postcolonial conflictological framework to explain the persistence of Riffian dissent and propose pathways toward ethnolinguistic justice. Combining traditional conflict models (e.g., Galtung's ABC-triangle and the conflict cycle) with postcolonial theory (neocolonialism, coloniality, epistemic violence), the study conceptualises the Rif as a protracted, postcolonial conflict shaped by systemic neglect, symbolic erasure, and structural repression. Through a multi-layered analysis of key historical events – including the Rif Revolt, 1984 Bread Riots, and the Hirak Rif – the thesis reveals how unresolved structural contradictions and state attitudes perpetuate cycles of violent behaviours. The analysis also critiques the comprador power dynamics and explores the role of language in shaping political exclusion. Finally, the study proposes a range of transformative justice mechanisms grounded in decolonial praxis, including symbolic recognition, linguistic redress, and pluralistic governance. So doing, it charts a path toward durable peace and ethnolinguistic equity in Morocco, and beyond.

Keywords: conflictology, postcolonial theory, decoloniality, Rif, Morocco, postcolonial conflictology

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POSITIONALITY STATEMENT

As a white, European, secular researcher, I am and must be aware of the power asymmetries embedded in researching postcolonial and Islamic contexts like Morocco. My personal proximity to Amazigh identity, through my partner's Central Atlas heritage, deepens my investment in the Riffian case, but also risks bias. While I do hold that the Riffians are the structurally oppressed party, I remain committed to presenting this analysis with reflexivity and intellectual honesty; it will not be advocacy disguised as scholarship – but true objectivism does not exist.

My apatheism³ further necessitates care when engaging with the role of Islam in this case. Though some may read Islam's presence as a colonial or imperial legacy, that view cannot erase the genuine spiritual and cultural significance of it for many Imazighen. I aim to approach this with respect, even if/when I hold it accountable.

Lastly, I acknowledge the weight of Euro-American epistemological dominance. These frameworks are not neutral, neither are the institutions. I try to mitigate this by integrating non-Western thinkers, remaining open to plurality, and making space for other voices. This research is admittedly subjective, but transparent. I do not claim to speak for the Rif, only to help highlight what has been repeatedly silenced and think of ways to approach justice.

³ The belief that neither the existence nor non-existence of god(s) is irrelevant. For clarity's sake, as a secularist, I believe religion should not play a significant role in collective life – it is a personal choice, a personal spirituality. I do lean more towards atheism, than any recognised faith.

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TERMINOLOGY LIST

<i>Amazigh</i> (plur: <i>Imazighen</i>)	Endonymic alternative to ‘Berber ⁴ ,’ an indigenous people of North Africa and the Sahel, this includes Riffians.
<i>Amazighité</i>	‘Amazighness,’ the being Amazigh.
<i>Darija</i>	Moroccan Colloquial Arabic
<i>Makhzen</i>	The (ruling) elites of Morocco – corporate leadership, the monarchy, politicians. Often used interchangeably with central government, but here expanded to include other establishment elites.
<i>Tamazight</i>	Amazigh languages, also used for Central Atlas Tamazight.
<i>Tarifit</i>	Riffian Tamazight.
Violence	Herein, violence is taken as any measure which violates one’s liberties and humanity, both personal and collective. Thus, it is not limited purely to physical expressions of such but also includes attacks on identity and its expression.

⁴ Warrants mentioning that most tribes/communities prefer to identify by their local identity, e.g., *Riffi*.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Riffians, an Amazigh population indigenous to northern Morocco, have endured a century of state and imperial violence – a history marked not by episodic unrest but by recurring resistance. In 1921, Mohamed ben Abdelkrim El Khattabi led a successful anti-colonial revolt against Spanish forces, declaring the short-lived Rif ‘Republic’ before its surrender to a joint French-Spanish military campaign in 1926 (Akouh, 2025). That legacy of defiance would live on to this day. Just two years after Moroccan independence in 1956, a Riffian uprising over exclusion and poverty was brutally suppressed through military means, under then-Prince Hassan’s supervision. The Rif Revolt (1958-59), as it became known, was followed by mass arrests, collective punishment, and long-term marginalisation (El Idrissi, 2014).

After decades of oppressive rule under now-King Hassan II, known as the Years of Lead, the Rif again made themselves known. As part of nationwide protests against austerity in 1984, the Nador Bread Riots were sparked by economic grievances, but also took a regionalist tone. Protesters sang songs and slogans denouncing the monarchy and central government, recalling the legacy of Abdelkrim. The Riots were suppressed with excessive violence (Suárez-Collado, 2023). Most recently, in 2016, the region erupted once more following the death of fishmonger Mohsin Fikri – crushed in a waste compactor while trying to retrieve confiscated goods, allegedly due to police action. The movement that followed, known as the Hirak Rif, demanded justice, infrastructure, healthcare, and dignity. It was met with mass arrests, accusations of separatism, and false convictions, lacking due process as expressed by Amnesty International (2017; 2018; Dieste, 2021). These four events – the War, Revolt, Riots, and Hirak – form the key nodes in a cycle of dissent and repression that defines the Riffian struggle, what Riffian-Belgian journalist Yassin Akouh (2025) calls the ‘*colonial curse*’.

What makes this topic urgent is not just the brutality or persistence of repression (Debackere & Akouh, 2021), but the failure of the Moroccan state and broader academic community to address the structural nature of the conflict. Each ‘subcycle’ ends the same way; protest is vilified, reforms are announced but remain lacking in implementation, dissent is punished, and the underlying injustices remain (Abouzzohour, 2021). Despite growing international attention – particularly during the Hirak – the fundamental dynamics have not changed. The cost of continued misframing and failed reform is high, not only in terms of

human rights, but also in the continued erasure of indigenous identity, the stalling of reconciliation, and the entrenchment of neocolonial power dynamics.

Most existing analyses treat the Rif as a regional grievance or lagging development – at best, the state as an example of authoritarian overreach, and, at worst, the Riffians as a threat to national security. Academia focuses on identity politics, human rights, and liberalisation, but the topic remains understudied as a whole. While important, these perspectives tend to describe what is happening without analysing why it repeats – never mind how it could change. They rarely engage with the structural and symbolic dimensions of conflict, nor with reproduction of colonial dynamics. By treating the Rif not as a regional irritation but as a case of protracted ethnolinguistic conflict rooted in colonial legacies, this thesis aims to contribute a new lens for understanding such struggles – and the violence concealed beneath supposed peace.

This thesis provides a proof of concept for a postcolonial conflictology (PCC). While conflictological frameworks and resolution methods succeed in changing behaviour and minimising their justifying attitudes, they fail to tackle the core contradictions that cause conflicts. Expanding conflictological tools, such as the conflict triangle (ABC-model) and narrative theory (de Sousa & de Oliveira, 2021; Cobb, 2013), with postcolonial theory – neocolonial continuity and internal colonialism in particular – allows us to more aptly approach ethnolinguistic and postcolonial conflicts. This applies to the understudied Riffian case in order to reframe questions from ‘why are they fighting?’ toward ‘what sustains this conflict – and how do we transform it?’ This leads to the central research question:

How can a postcolonial conflictological approach reframe the Riffian struggle and illuminate pathways toward ethnolinguistic justice?

To answer this, the thesis undertakes a qualitative case study of the Rif, applying (postcolonial) conflict analysis and resolution alongside textual and historical analysis. It examines protest, repression, and representation from the colonial period (1904) to the present (2025), mapping how violence is enacted and legitimised, and how the struggle has been narrativised – by the state, its critics, and Riffians themselves.

The following two chapters inform the foundations of the analysis, firstly the theoretical framework and key concepts, then the methodology. Chapters four through six contain the analysis, organised by theme. This is followed by my conclusion and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter outlines the theoretical framework for this thesis: conflictology, postcolonial theory, and their synthesis.

2.1. CONFLICTOLOGY

Omoluabi (2001) defines conflictology as the study of disharmonious relationships between groups. It identifies causes, traces patterns, and proposes strategies for resolution. Crucially, conflictology is not just analytic but also transformative; it aims to shift the conditions that make conflict seem inevitable.

The field is multidisciplinary, this disciplinary flexibility makes it especially useful in postcolonial contexts, where conflict is rarely confined to territory or policy but embedded in identity, memory, and meaning. As Vinyamata (2010) notes, conflictology is rooted in principles of non-violence and encompasses what Omoluabi (2001) calls the full ‘anatomy of conflict,’ including resolution, transformation, and management. It enables simultaneous attention to structural asymmetries, relational breakdowns, and the narrative framings that sustain them.

2.1.1. MODELS & DIMENSIONS OF CONFLICT

The foremost conflictological models, the conflict triangle and cycle, as illustrated here by Galtung’s ABC-model and de Sousa & de Oliveira’s iteration of the cycle.

Galtung’s ABC-model (figure 1) outlines three interdependent components of conflict:

- **Attitudes** parties hold about themselves and one another – distrust, perceptions, etc.
- Parties’ observable **behaviour**, whether cooperative, confrontational, or violent.
- Underlying **contradictions** between parties’ interests, values, or needs.

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Figure 1. ABC-model, or Conflict Triangle
 (adapted from Galtung, in de Sousa & de Oliveira, 2021)

In this model, these components reinforce one another. Contradictions give rise to attitudes; attitudes shape behaviour, and, in turn, behaviour influences both. This model, thus, underscores that conflict is not a moment but a pattern – one rooted in unresolved contradiction, reinforced through behaviour, and justified through narrative. However, its subsumption of C as a mere component is odd, as it provides the primary cause and motivation for conflict.

These components are mapped in de Sousa & de Oliveira’s (2021) conflict cycle (figure 2), which concerns a dynamic model illustrating the (de)escalation of conflict through five levels of intensity: stable and unstable peace, conflict, crisis, and war.

Figure 2. The Conflict Cycle (adapted from de Sousa & de Oliveira, 2021)

	Conflict intensity	Escalation	De-escalation	Relevant vertex of ABC-model	Interaction Strategy	Perception of 'other'	Method of change
War	War			Behaviour	Zero-Sum	Enemy	
Negative Peace	Crisis			Behaviour	Win-Lose	Enemy/Rival	Violence
	Conflict			Attitude	Win-Lose	Rival	Threats of violence
	Unstable Peace			Goals	Compromise	Friend	
	Stable Peace			Goals	Win-Win	Friend	Courts
Positive Peace	Durable Peace						

Transitions between these levels are triggered by shifts in one or more of the ABC components. Catalytic events may function as flashpoints, but they emerge from pre-existing contradictions, attitudes, and behaviours. As Omoyefa (2014) stresses, most conflict is driven by unmet human needs and unresolved contradictions, not spontaneous hostilities.

The transition from instability to conflict is marked by a shift in attitudes, specifically the conception of the ‘other’ as a ‘rival.’ This enables behavioural escalation. Next, a crisis is

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

CONFLICTOLOGY

marked by credible threats or acts of violence. While this model successfully charts escalations in negative perceptions and violent behaviours, it fails to adequately map nonviolent (at least physically) behaviours and broader attitudinal aspects, such as narrative hegemony. Moreover, it overlooks the contradictions at the root of conflict. The model remains of merit when plotting escalatory peaks of conflict, hence it will still be used.

De Sousa & de Oliveira (2021) argue that the cycle's phases reflect **negative peace** – the absence of physical violence without social justice. Durable, **positive peace** requires transforming *all three* elements of the triangle. To that end, and while the paper will remain structured around the ABC-framework, I attach the following three dimensions to them: structural, systemic, and symbolic. Each offers a distinct but interlocking dimension of how conflicts develop, persist, and may be transformed.

Structural Contradictions

Galtung views conflict as an “*incompatibility of goals and a struggle of opposing ideas [and] values*” (in de Sousa & de Oliveira, 2021, p. x). His work focuses on the contradictions that underlie conflict: mismatched needs, interests, and structures of power. These contradictions manifest in political, economic, and cultural forms and will drive persistent injustice unless addressed. In the Rif, these contradictions appear in the form of ethnolinguistic marginalisation, political exclusion, and economic neglect.

The shortcoming of this framework is the relative shallowness of the contradiction. In many cases, such as the Rif, the contradiction is no matter of winning natural resources, but a structural denial of self-actualisation.

Systemic Behaviour

Gorvein (2009) approaches conflict as a system governed by feedback loops. Conflict, here, escalates in cycles: from tension to rupture, then resets under new conditions that often reproduce the same dynamics. The cycle may appear broken but is actually dormant. This lens helps explain the repetitive nature of Riffian resistance and state repression over the past century – protest begets repression; repression begets protest. It warrants clarifying that both I and Galtung (2000) consider violence to be more than physical, but also systemic and cultural

– or, by my own definition, any action which violates one’s humanity or peoplehood, such as linguistic marginalisation.

Symbolic Hegemony: Attitudes

Cobb (2013) defines conflict as a struggle over legitimacy. As conflict escalates, narratives become simplified and closed – one party is rational, the other deviant, wrong, illegitimate. This narrative closure limits the space for resolution by denying complexity and mutual recognition. In the Rif, this is evident in the persistent narrative framing of dissent as separatist or criminal, rather than reformist or political.

Here, I ascribe narratives to the narrow perception-based attitude-component. These narratives include the nationalist myths and history but are also expanded to justifications of violence. Altogether, these perspectives – structural, systemic, symbolic (3S) – allow us to interrogate how the Riffian conflict is structured, how it repeats, and how it is framed more aptly.

2.1.2. CONFLICT TRANSFORMATION

What sets conflictology apart from conventional models is its emphasis on transformation over analysis. Rather than just halting violence, it addresses the deep causes: structural injustice, harmful narratives, and broken relationships.

Galtung’s TRANSCEND method (2000) reflects this principle. It seeks to:

- Resolve **contradictions** by addressing core structural issues,
- Transform **attitudes** by fostering empathy and mutual recognition, and
- Change **behaviour** through constructive engagement.

In doing so, it breaks Gorvein’s feedback loops and opens Cobb’s narrative closure. Again, durable, positive peace, in this view, must engage all three elements of the ABC model – not only to end conflict, but to enable justice. However, it overlooks the additional elements established by 3S, this claim will be substantiated throughout the following two sections (2.2. & 2.3.).

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POSTCOLONIAL THEORY

This transformation may be achieved through reconciliation – reciprocal legitimisation and re-establishing relationships (Cobb, 2013; Strupinskienė, 2016). Strupinskienė’s model of reconciliation operates at three levels – individual, communal, national – each ranging from surface-level (thin) to structural (thick). Approaches may be top-down or bottom-up, but she argues that a combination of both is necessary in most cases.

Reconciliation cannot go without justice, however. Justice is a fraught topic. Primarily, justice can be retributive or restorative, i.e., punitive or reconciliatory (Cohen, 2016; Wenzel & Okimoto, 2016). The latter is the paradigm in post-conflict and transitional justice. These, however, assume a before-and-after violence (Kent, 2016; Lie *et al.*, 2006), unfit for my inclusion of epistemic, narrative, and systemic violence, which, as is the case in the Rif, often carry on far beyond physically violent episodes. These violences are inherent to postcolonial domination, as explored in the next section.

2.2. POSTCOLONIAL THEORY

Postcolonial theory explains how colonial logic persists after formal independence – how it shapes identities, knowledge, and structure. It complements – or completes – conflictology by focusing on the reproduction of imperial frameworks and the legitimisation of marginalisation – the contradictions and the attitudes.

2.2.1. NEOCOLONIALISM & INTERNAL COLONIALISM

Postcolonial thought reveals how colonial legacies persist, thereby sustaining economic, cultural, and intellectual hierarchies (Said, 1994; Ben Barka, 1977). **Neocolonialism** – the indirect continuation of imperial domination – includes both foreign manipulation (through, e.g., the global market) and the internal reproduction of colonial power structures. As argued by Fanon (1963; 1986), Césaire (2000), and Cabral (2016), formal independence often boils down to a handing down of power to local elites who preserve colonial interests, often under a nationalist guise.

Ben Barka (1960) called this dynamic ‘disguised colonialism’ – liberal capitalist powers maintain influence through economic leverage and ideological co-option. In this context, the national bourgeoisie elites function as a **comprador class**, as described by wa Thiong’o (1993)

and Fanon (1963). These elites mediate between external interests and internal populations and, despite their local or indigenous origins, legitimise the new colonialism by aligning with foreign capital, silencing dissent, and replicating colonial governance methods. Fanon (1963) and Ben Barka (1960; 1962) warned that unless the national elite is dismantled or transformed, postcolonial society will continue to reproduce the inequalities and hierarchies of the regime.

This process can thus also manifest internally, particularly in the marginalisation of ethnic minorities or peripheral regions. **Internal colonialism** refers to the reproduction of imperial core-periphery dynamics within a single nation-state – centralised control, resource extraction, and cultural domination. This Leninist⁵ critique was also echoed by Blauner (1969) in the context of racialised communities in the US and J. Turner (2018), who levelled it directly at postcolonial states, showing how nationalist regimes often recreate colonial modes of exclusion. Similar patterns can be observed in cases such as the Māori in Aotearoa, where the central government treats peripheral ethnic regions as internal colonies (Pool, 2017), and especially Morocco’s treatment of the Sahrawi (Munene, 2010). It is in this sense that the term most applies to the Rif; marginalisation stems not from foreign occupation, but the domestic elite that inherited and repurposed colonial methods; one part of how the Rif’s structural domination manifests.

2.2.2. COLONIALITY & EPISTEMIC VIOLENCE

While neocolonialism describes material and institutional continuities, **coloniality** considers the more socio-psychological, systemic reproduction of colonialism at the level of knowledge, language, and legitimacy. Quijano (2000) intended it to describe how colonial categories – race, modernity, civilisation – continue to structure postcolonial power hierarchies. Mignolo (2010) expands this to epistemology, Eurocentric knowledge is privileged, and the indigenous erased, dismissed, or silenced. They argue that modernity – and liberalism – cannot be disentangled from colonial domination.

Maldonado-Torres (2007) and Grosfoguel (2007) also argue that coloniality not only dominates economically and politically, but also ontologically and epistemologically. The colonised are not only dispossessed, but also dehumanised and delegitimised. Fanon (1986) and wa Thiong’o (1994) emphasise the systemic role of cultural alienation. Through the

⁵ Specifically, Lenin’s *Imperialism: The Highest Stage of Capitalism* (2010).

imposition of colonial languages and epistemologies, the colonised are estranged from their histories and identities. In the Moroccan context, the prestige of French and dominance of Arabic are such legacies which marginalise Amazigh identity and delegitimise their civilisation. Césaire (2000) described colonisation as tearing “*millions from their gods, their land, their habits, their life*” (p. 43). This severance continues in subtle yet pervasive ways, through education, media, national myths, and narratives. These processes constitute **epistemic violence** – the systematic exclusion and devaluation of ways of knowing, remembering, and resisting that challenge the dominant.

When postcolonial states fail to confront these hierarchies, they not only perpetuate inequality but legitimise it. This has direct implications for justice: any postcolonial justice must go beyond material redress to include the reclamation of memory, language, and narrative. It must acknowledge the complicity of comprador elites and the state in maintaining coloniality.

2.2.3. SYMBOLIC DOMINATION

Colonial and postcolonial power is not sustained solely through force, but also through narrative. Said (2003) and Fanon (1963) demonstrate how colonised peoples are discursively construed as irrational, backwards, or violent, framing them as threats to order and development. These narrative framings maintain hierarchy by legitimising and justifying exclusion.

Cobb’s (2013) aforementioned theory of conflict is relevant here. The closure of narratives takes the form of national myths, hero narratives, and security discourses that erase, diminish, or criminalise counter-narratives and histories. In Morocco, tropes of a lawless, separatist, or ungrateful Rif serve to exclude the Riffian claims from political legitimacy and justify state repression (Rhani *et al.*, 2020; Chtatou, 2017). This symbolic domination is **narrative violence**, reinforced by power imbalances and cultural/narrative hegemony (Gramsci, 1999). It forecloses recognition and reduces political struggle. It is the key mechanism of internal colonialism, rendering the marginalised as internal ‘others’ who threaten national unity.

A final element crucial to comprehend is **linguicism** – the structural discrimination against individuals based on their language. As per Reyhner (2013), linguicism occurs when language hierarchies are constructed and enforced to the detriment of minority languages. His

research focuses on Indigenous American languages, but other examples include Basque and, indeed, Tamazight. In (post)colonial states, these hierarchies frequently align with broader ethnic or cultural exclusion.

In the Moroccan context, Arabic and French function as dominant languages of administration, business, education, and media. Tamazight has historically been excluded from key public domains (Aadnani, 2001; El Aissati, 2001). This mirrors colonial ‘civilising’ discourses, where indigenous languages were labelled as “*barbarous dialects*” (Crawford, 2007, p. 47) and actively suppressed under the guise of progress, forcing a choice between identity and success (Reyhner, 2010; 2017; Ali, 2018). Such policies continue to marginalise Amazigh identity by rendering their languages unofficial, non-modern, or invisible.

Linguicism compounds symbolic marginalisation by influencing self-perception, social mobility, and intergenerational transmission. Stigmatisation of Tamazight leads to shame, code-switching, or complete abandonment as indicated by El Guabli (2021; 2022) and Louffi (2021). This reinforces the epistemic violence: if your language is unrecognised, so too is your worldview.

Therefore, ultimately, linguicism not only limits communication, it delegitimises identity. In conflict contexts, this deepens the contradiction between the state’s claims to unity and its refusal to acknowledge plurality. Linguicism, then, is not just prejudice, but a symbolic mechanism of exclusion. Understanding these narrative dynamics is, thus, essential for any project of postcolonial justice, as only by restoring the legitimacy of the marginalised and reopening the narrative can meaningful transformation become possible. This sets the stage for the following section: a dialogue between conflictology and postcolonialism; I propose a postcolonial conflictological framework.

2.3. TOWARD A POSTCOLONIAL CONFLICTOLOGY

The preceding sections outlined two distinct but complementary frameworks. Conflictology, examining the structural, systemic, and symbolic dynamics of protracted conflict, and postcolonial theory, interrogating the persistence of colonial logic. Here, I propose a synthesis – a **postcolonial conflictology** – as the most appropriate lens for cases like the Rif, where conflict is not only cyclical but deeply embedded in ideology, history, and epistemology.

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In postcolonial contexts, injustice often persists not due to unresolved disputes alone, but because the very foundations of the state remain colonially structured. The contradiction is not simply between groups but between marginalised communities and inherited systems that devalue their identity, erase their history, and suppress their legitimacy. Conflictology offers tools to analyse these patterns, but without understanding coloniality, it cannot interrogate their origins – it risks misdiagnosing symptoms as causes. Together, these frameworks allow us to add value to action.

ABC is shaped by this coloniality. Structural contradictions, as uneven power dynamics and marginalisation, are shaped by neocolonial structures and cultural erasure – all legacies of colonial policy under nationalist rule. Symbolically, attitudes are shaped by Maldonado-Torres' (2007) 'coloniality of being' – the inherited belief that some groups are more civilised, modern, or even human than others. These hierarchies persist in contemporary state rhetoric, media, and political discourse. Behaviours, such as repression and surveillance, are not spontaneous but reflect embedded systems of control, institutionalised through colonial precedent and postcolonial mimicry. Gorvein (2009) explains their cyclical logic, but postcolonial theory exposes its intentionality. To echo Fanon (1963), the colonised adopts the coloniser's violent nature.

Narrative theory intersects here: as conflict escalates, the state simplifies and rejects competing narratives by casting them as criminal or deviant. Mignolo (2010) and Grosfoguel (2007) identified this as epistemic violence, the suppression of alternative histories, worldviews, and indeed futures. These are no collateral effects of conflict, but inherent to colonial domination. By foregrounding the oppressed and exposing the systems of domination, narrative hegemony becomes undermined, thereby cutting through dominant narratives where previous approaches have fallen prey to them⁶.

In such contexts, justice must be reimagined. Currently, peace and justice are often seen as incompatible. In the restorative sense, one forgoes justice to achieve peace by prioritising reconciliation mechanisms like truth commissions and amnesties, and, traditionally, in retributive senses, you risk peace for justice by potentially triggering more/heightened conflict. I argue, however, that in cases of foundational violence, as in the Rif, these stances fall short.

⁶ As is the case, I argue, in Palestine and Cyprus, where the Zionist and Greek Cypriot narratives are taken at face-value too often and the Palestinian and Turkish Cypriot overlooked. The Cypriot case is often reduced to a Turkish invasion and forced resettlement, overlooking the decades of Greek-to-Turkish Cypriot violence and displacement and the Greek putsch that 'motivated' the invasion according to the Turkish narrative (Menelaou, 2019), as an example.

Therefore, by recognising the ontological nature of conflict, postcolonial justice (PCJ) sees peace *as* justice; it aims not just to reconcile or punish but transform – and that can only be possible when ‘invisible’ violences are absent.

PCJ extends the focus of conflict transformation beyond behaviour and institutions to matters of identity, collective memory, and legitimacy. It echoes Galtung’s TRANSCEND method, but demands deeper, ontological change through the following:

- **Narrative redress:** reclaiming erased histories and discredited epistemologies,
- **Cultural redress:** relegitimising indigenous and minority languages, symbols, and knowledges,
- **Structural transformation:** dismantling comprador elites and inherited hierarchies.

These imperatives align with 3S – symbolic, structural, and systemic respectively⁷ – to enable what C. Turner (2013) calls a progress narrative: a shared reckoning with the past, to enable a common future. When that past is denied or distorted, such transitions remain performative, as is the case in Morocco, where the Equity and Reconciliation Commission (ERC) failed to address the architecture of violence (Colin, 2024; El Idrissi, 2014). It is thereby, that I suggest a parallel process to Strupinskienė’s three levels of reconciliation, ontological reconciliation – not just the restoration of knowledge (epistemology), but the restoration of being, the legitimisation of existence, identity, and memory, without which the others cannot be achieved.

⁷ Structural in this sense implies the legislative, administrative, and governmental definition – these enable the behavioural, systemic aspect.

3. METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the methodological framework used to apply the postcolonial conflictological approach to the Riffian case. It integrates textual and historical analysis with conflict analysis and resolution (CAR), enabling a multi-dimensional reading of the case across structure, system, and symbol. The aim is not only to trace the evolution of the conflict, but to interrogate how it has been framed and misrepresented, and why it remains unsolved.

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

This research employs a qualitative single-case study design. Such enables detailed, context-sensitive investigation of complex social conflicts, well-suited for politically silenced, historically embedded cases such as the Rif.

The study adopts an interpretivist paradigm, grounded in the belief that legitimacy, identity, and perception are constitutive parts of conflict. As shown in 2.1., conflictology explicitly recognises that such attitudes and narratives play a foundational role in both escalation and transformation. Therefore, the study is concerned with the factual history and how the conflict is constructed and remembered.

3.2. DATA COLLECTION & ANALYSIS

This study relies exclusively on textual data, both primary (reports, speeches, official documentation) and secondary (academia, media coverage). The studied period spans from 1904 to today.

Data was selected using purposive sampling, based on the following criteria:

- Relevance to the case (e.g. events, policies),
- Relevance to the framework (e.g. epistemic violence, narrative theory),
- Credibility and transparency,
- Public accessibility.

This was done through online resources like Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Research Rabbit, and guided by specific key terms (see Appendix 4). These include historical events, theoretical concepts, and key thinkers.

The analysis is conducted through two interconnected methods: textual and historical analysis, which inform CAR. This order reflects the ontological stance of the research: history and narrative shape structure, a premise central to the PCC framework. Conflict analysis must begin with how conflict is *constructed, narrated, and internalised*.

Textual & Historical Analysis

This method provides the chronological and discursive context for the conflict. It maps key episodes of dissent and repression, in doing so tracing shifts in discourse, attitudes, and behaviours across time.

Textual analysis focuses on the framing and narrativisation of the Riffian struggle – especially by the Moroccan state and media, but also by the Riffians themselves. These include themes of securitisation and betrayal, which are read as mechanisms of narrative closure and symbolic domination (see 2.2. and Cobb, 2013). This reflects PCC’s emphasis on epistemic violence and narrative as a tool of coloniality. While this draws on elements of discourse analysis, I avoid any claim of such due to language limitations. Instead, it relies on secondary interpretations and meta-analysis.

Historical analysis constructs a timeline of dissent and repression, identifying periods of escalation. It pays special attention to internal ruptures (the four core events) and external influences (colonial policies, geopolitics). Where useful, comparative examples of similar cases of peripheral, ethnolinguistic, or indigenous struggles are called upon (like the Sahrawi).

This dual analytic foundation lays the groundwork for a PCC reading, one which moves beyond sequence to interrogating how violence and silence are structured, justified, and reproduced.

Conflict Analysis & Resolution (CAR)

CAR is used to organise and interrogate the findings. It applies the ABC-model and conflict cycle alongside the 3S dimensions (structure, system, symbol) – as outlined in 2.1.2. – to map how conflict is reproduced. However, these tools are adapted through the PCC lens, including a reframing of the ABC-model into the contradiction spiral – see 2.3.

3. METHODOLOGY

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS & LIMITATIONS

Particular attention is given to:

- Persistent contradictions and grievances,
- How state and Riffian actors frame and respond to dissent,
- Previous resolution efforts and their shortcomings,
- The role of narrative closure and coloniality in blocking transformation.

The contradiction spiral proposed here recasts attitudes as justifications of contradictions and behaviours as manifestations of them – thus positioning contradictions as the engine rather than a component of conflict. This layered reading allows for a deeper diagnosis of the conflict's longevity and exposes its colonial legacy. Ultimately, this section seeks to demonstrate the analytical power of PCC as both a diagnostic and transformative tool.

3.3. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS & LIMITATIONS

Studying an ongoing, unresolved conflict always demands care. Historical accounts are often partial, contested, or politicised – and Moroccan culture tends to be silent on taboo topics⁸ (El Idrissi, 2014). Therefore, triangulation is used to mitigate source-bias, and interpretations are made with caution, sourcing, transparency, and reflexivity.

All data is drawn from publicly available, legally accessible materials. Sources are selected with attention to positionality and voice; wherever possible, I prefer to let the Riffians and Amazigh speak. All sources are in English or Dutch, but it incorporates translations of and reactions to French and Arabic sources where possible – I acknowledge this as a limitation.

My personal positionality as the researcher must also be noted. As a European apatheist⁹, I need to be wary of my secular attitudes when dealing with a deeply Islamic culture. Moreover, my proximity to Amazigh identity may cause bias; I need be vigilant, humble, and reflexive throughout. The aim, here, as in anything I write, is not to speak for, but to help make space for the unspoken or unheard.

This research is also fundamentally a proof of concept. Its findings may not be generalisable as it is case-specific, but the testing of PCC is intended to demonstrate its utility and value and provoke further application and adaptations of the framework.

⁸ In part due to censorship laws.

⁹ To repeat, I neither believe nor disbelieve, I find it irrelevant. For clarity's sake, I lean more atheist.

4. SYSTEMIC VIOLENCE

This chapter explores the surface level – what is happening? To do so, I use the conflict cycle to examine how dissent-repression behaviours have hardened into patterns – Gorvein’s feedback loops. These events are not isolated incidents but natural reactions to unresolved contradictions, these will be covered in the next chapter. Here, the system is laid bare to chart the case – the symptoms identified.

4.1. THE COLONIAL CYCLE (1904-1956)

Early colonial times saw cooperation between Spanish authorities and Riffian elites, most prominently *qaid*¹⁰ El Khattabi (Akouh, 2025). Some Riffians, like El Khattabi, saw the Spanish as potential collaborators, who would hopefully bring European technology and modernity, because of longstanding trade relations with Melilla and comparison to the brutal French dominations in neighbouring Algeria – after all, Spain’s power had long waned (Sbaa & Akouh, 2025a). Upon formalisation of the Protectorate (1912), however, Spanish overreach disillusioned the El Khattabi family. For example, the *qaid*’s son, Abdelkrim¹¹, was arrested over his anticolonial opinions.

The contradiction of goals became clear: colonial subjugation vs. Riffian agency. After the *qaid*’s death, Abdelkrim and his brother Si Mohammed led a group of rebels to decisively reject colonial control, marked by Spanish defeat at the Annual (1921) (Akouh, 2025). This developed into the Rif War (1921-26) and the declaration of an independent Rif. In 1923, the Spanish began to deploy chemical weapons, including against civilian targets. This marked a behavioural change, from containment to annihilation. In 1926, a united French-Spanish force led to Abdelkrim’s surrender and exile.

The war was lost, but the anticolonial spirit never left. The Riffians played a notable role in resisting the French as the core contradiction – colonialism vs. autonomy – was never resolved, and the Rif remained in conflict with colonial forces until independence. This timeline is shown in Figure 3.

¹⁰ A *qaid* is a Muslim judge.

¹¹ Full name: Mohammed ben Abdelkrim El Khattabi. Popularly and herein referred to by his patronym.

4. SYSTEMIC VIOLENCE
THE POSTCOLONIAL CYCLE (1956-1999)

Figure 3. The Colonial Cycle

The key takeaway of this era is the legacy of Spanish chemical warfare, which is still felt today in the Riffian cancer rates, the highest in the country by far (European Parliament, 2021). To date, Spain has taken no accountability, nor apologised (Sbaa & Akouh, 2025a). The Rif ‘Republic’ and Abdelkrim legacies remain massive in the Rif to this day, including in more modern movements, but it must be stressed that the ‘Republic’ was only ever referred to as such in European discourse, never in internal documents. Akouh (2025) explains that, although critical of the Sultan’s inaction, the state was strongly anticolonial but loyal to Morocco. Nonetheless, this misconception is weaponised to discredit Riffian claims as secessionist (Dieste, 2021; Hart, 1972).

4.2. THE POSTCOLONIAL CYCLE (1956-1999)

Postcolonial statebuilding is a trying time for any nation. For the Rif, the reintegration saw the enforcement of French on the hitherto Spanish, Arabic, and Tamazight speaking region as well as perceived economic neglect (Rhani *et al.*, 2020; Ahmed & Akins, 2012). The contradiction at the heart of this era was regionalism vs. state nationalism – a struggle for recognition and demarginalisation that quickly escalated into defiance.

As calls for justice went unanswered by the makhzen, Riffians mobilised in a mass protest movement demanding political representation and economic investment. The state’s behavioural response was brutal. Military forces, led by then-Crown Prince Hassan II, violently suppressed the uprising now known as the Rif Revolt (1958–59), with atrocities against civilians starkly documented in El Idrissi’s *Briser le Silence* (2014).

In the aftermath, the region was effectively militarised, economic marginalisation worsened, and repression deepened. This era, the ‘Years of Lead,’ was marked by Hassan’s authoritarian rule: censorship, secret prisons such as Tazmamart, and the violent crushing of dissent (Amine, 2016; El Guabli, 2020; Menin, 2019) – the Rif was transported to the rest of his realm. Attitudes hardened, the state saw resistance as betrayal and thus Riffian grievance as disloyalty.

Then, in 1984, a series of national protests and riots, known as the Bread Riots, broke out over economic demands. The Riffian episode in Nador had a pronounced Riffian element to it, however. Demands were strongly tied to tariffs with Melilla, but it also took a remarkably antimonarchical tone (Suárez-Collado, 2023). These riots constituted the first major event in which Riffians recalled their legacy of resistance, such as Abdelkrim and the ‘Republic.’ Government response was once again violent, but not military. After the Riots, things quieted down in Morocco as external pressure forced Hassan to relax some more tyrannical practices, until his death in 1999.

Figure 4. The Postcolonial Cycle

This period makes the emergence of an internal colonial dynamic clear: the Rif was no longer just marginalised, but peripheralised. The contradiction of state nationalism vs. regional identity was never resolved, as proven by the remarkable similarity in the demands of the Revolt and the most recent episode (Akouh, 2025; Akarkach, 2018), the Hirak, and the nostalgic invocations during the Riots.

4.3. THE CONTEMPORARY CYCLE (1999-)

The latest, and contemporary, cycle begins in 1999, with the ascension of Mohammed VI, who faced the arduous task of maintaining his authority while effectively liberalising, surrounded by a citizenry tainted by decades of repression and his father’s corrupt cronies. One of his early gestures was the establishment of the Equity and Reconciliation Committee (ERC) in 2004, a symbolic attempt to address his father’s abuses, though it fell short of true accountability or reform.

The ‘Arab’ Spring of 2011 also made it to Morocco. Here, however, it was quickly manoeuvred as the King pre-empted mass mobilisation by announcing constitutional reforms. Among them, finally, the recognition of Tamazight – an unprecedented win for Amazigh cultural rights. Yet, beneath the liberal veneer, the old contradiction endured, waiting for a catalyst.

In late 2016, it came. A Riffian fishmonger was crushed to death in a rubbish truck while retrieving confiscated goods. Footage of the event and eyewitness accusations of police culpability triggered a wave of protests in Al Hoceima. This call for justice and accountability rapidly evolved into a mass movement: the Hirak Rif. Protestors demanded an end to economic neglect, marginalisation, and cultural erasure (Dieste, 2021). Once again, the state responded with repression: crackdowns, mass arrests, and false, vague accusations of separatism (Akarkach, 2018; Marijnissen *et al.*, 2020). A key figure, Nasser Zefzafi, was tried without due process and handed an arbitrarily long prison sentence, a violation of human rights as per Amnesty International (2018; 2019). Since, the state has made various promises, but nothing has changed. The Rif is still marginalised, denied, silenced.

Figure 5. The Contemporary Cycle

4.4. WHAT THE PATTERNS TELL US

Throughout, we have seen several peaks of conflict (Figure 6), marked by a change in Riffian attitude to activism and a state behavioural response of repression. The Rif has consistently experienced **marginalisation and neglect**, marked by social injustice, economic exclusion, and persistent underdevelopment. ‘Seeming abandonment’ after the Revolt and decades of marginalisation sparked the Bread Riots, as indicated by Alvarado (2023), Suárez-Collado (2023), and by the subjects in El Idrissi’s documentary (2014).

Figure 6. The Riffian Cycle

This marginalisation generates **dissent** (protest and resistance). The state then responds with **repression**, securitisation, and narrative delegitimation. Little to nothing changes, core demands remain unmet, and the cycle repeats. I have generalised this into the Behaviour Loop (Figure 7). Abbouzohour (2021), El Hamamouchi (2022) and the 2022 Human Rights Watch report also discuss this cycle and system of repression.

Figure 7. The Behaviour Loop

Crucially, the contradicting goals have remained largely the same since Moroccan independence; structural contradictions such as cultural erasure and regional neglect remain unchanged, hence why dissent reoccurs. To understand why the cycle resets, we must dig beneath the surface to confront the contradictions that sustain it. This will be further explained in the next chapter.

5. ETHNOLINGUISTIC INJUSTICE

This section concerns the engine of the conflict. It exposes the contradictions and symbolic violence that underlie the visible repression: a neocolonial state built on Arab-Islamic hegemony ruling over Amazigh peripheries, where tokenism and neglect masquerade as unity. The Rif is not marginal by accident – it is structurally excluded. The makhzen functions as a comprador class, mediating between foreign interests and domestic legitimacy, masking systemic injustice behind selective development and staged reform. At the same time, resistance is delegitimised through narrative closure – a symbolic process in which the Riffian becomes not merely secondary, but criminal. Until these contradictions are redressed and the stories that justify them dismantled, peace remains negative: a pause under pressure, not a transformation. This chapter addresses contradiction and attitude together, showing how one justifies the other and how both are reinforced through language.

5.1. STRUCTURAL INJUSTICE

The recurring conflict in the Rif is not a series of isolated outbursts; it is the logical product of a structural contradiction. The Moroccan state claims national unity while systematically marginalising the Rif – politically, economically, and culturally. This is no accident, but the design of a postcolonial system that inherited and adapted colonial domination.

Following the Revolt, the region was subjected to a military occupation that has never truly lifted. Police and gendarmerie presence is permanent, particularly in Al Hoceima province, with activists and their families subjected to routine harassment, surveillance, and movement restrictions (Alvarado, 2023). The state's use of Israeli-American spyware and the relocation of Hirak prisoners to distant prisons reveal a strategy of deterrence and fragmentation. The Rif is not simply administered; it is policed as an internal colony.

Economic marginalisation reinforces this subjugation. Despite the Rif's historical contributions, it remains systemically underdeveloped. Infrastructure, healthcare¹², and education consistently lag behind national averages, fuelling both the Revolt and the Hirak (Akarkach, 2018; Rhani *et al.*, 2020; Alvarado, 2023). Economic sanctions after the Revolt

¹² Particularly arduous since the Rif has the highest cancer rates in the nation, a legacy of Spanish chemical warfare, with 80% of adults and 50% of children with cancer being from repeatedly bombed areas. Spain has as of yet not apologised by any capacity (European Parliament, 2021).

starved the region of its domestic wealth, forcing migration (particularly to Europe) and weakening local economies and (oral) cultural transmission (Akouh & Akarkach, personal communication, April 7, 2025)¹³. Rather than empowering the Rif, state policy sought to pacify and displace – temporarily muting resistance while sowing the seed for further dissent.

Culturally, Riffian and Amazigh identities have been systematically undermined. Arabic and French dominate education, administration, and media, relegating Tamazight to the private sphere (Aadnani, 2001; El Guabli, 2021). Arabisation campaigns mirror colonial ‘civilising’ missions, denigrating indigenous languages as primitive – even extending to Colloquial Arabic (Darija) (Crawford, 2007; El Guabli, 2021; 2022). This rejection of Riffian cultural and linguistic recognition constitutes epistemic violence, severing communities from their own heritage. More gravely, it amounts to ontological violence: an all-out assault on the very being of Riffians as legitimate Moroccan subjects – cultural genocide?

These exclusions are deliberate. Ben Barka (1960) warned that Morocco’s independence merely replaced colonial elites with local compradors. The negotiated, compromised independence preserved colonial economic and administrative structures, resulting in Ben Kaddour’s (1972) *neo-makhzen*, which sustained the dominance of the ‘unproductive middlemen’ who served foreign and domestic capital over people – read: comprador elite (Ben Barka, 1962; 1977). Ben Barka’s denunciation of Morocco’s 1963 invasion of Algeria as a neocolonial betrayal of African liberation further illustrates this continuity (Ben Barka, 1963); Morocco not only inherited the mechanisms but also the mentality of empire.

The Rif is thus marginalised by design. Its historical demands – autonomy, dignity, recognition – remain unmet. As long as structural, political, and cultural injustices endure, dissent will not be anomalous, but rational and consequential.

5.2. SYMBOLIC INJUSTICE

Symbolic violence sustains the structural marginalisation of the Rif. Narrative closure – the closing off of legitimate counter-histories – plays a significant role in delegitimising Riffian identity and resistance. Language, likewise, is a crucial aspect; it is the vessel of identity, memory, and legitimacy to the Riffians. As King (2009) asserts, “*language is life.*” In Morocco,

¹³ I attended a discussion panel on Akouh’s book *Koloniale Vloek* (2025).

Tamazight has become an act of resistance against Arab-Islamic hegemony (Aadnani, 2001; El Aissati, 2001).

5.2.1. NARRATIVE CLOSURE

Moroccan national unity, framed through pan-Arabist Arabo-Islamic identity, marginalises Amazighité by depicting Riffian history as rebellious and treacherous. Uprisings such as the Revolt and Hirak are thus framed as separatist threats to national integrity, rather than legitimate demands for justice (Rhani *et al.*, 2020; Wolf, 2018; Monjib, 2018). This delegitimisation serves to vilify Riffian calls for justice.

Epistemically, Riffian history is erased. Abdelkrim, once a symbol of anti-colonial resistance, remains largely excluded from Morocco's historical canon – evidenced by his disappearance from it in 1926 despite his continued work from exile in Cairo, where he would pass away, having never returned to his homeland (Akouh, 2025; Wolf, 2018). Oral histories, crucial to Amazigh cultural transmission, are suppressed through Morocco's censorship and taboo-culture of silence, weakening the community's ability to sustain its counter-narratives (Rhani *et al.*, 2020; Aadnani, 2001). Aïdi (2020) calls the Riffian movements' invocation of historical figures (Abdelkrim, Ameziane, Jugurtha) an effort to reclaim this silenced legacy.

Arab nationalist narratives, underpinned by the (actually colonial¹⁴) 'Berber Myth' and the consequent 'Arab North Africa Myth' further enforce this exclusion. Amazighité is either dismissed as a colonial invention, such as pan-Arabist Libyan dictator Qaddafi, "*we the Berbers are the Arabs,*" or framed as subordinate to Arab, reinforcing their symbolic annihilation (El Kirat El Allame, 2009; MEMRI, 2007a). As per Belkacem Lounes, in response to Qaddafi, *there is no worse colonialism than that of the pan-Arabist clan that wants to dominate our people*, and "*thinking that diversity is a danger is an archaic and totalitarian idea*" (MEMRI, 2007b). Unfortunately, rather than pursuing a (civic) nationalism based on plurality and shared colonial trauma, the makhzen has opted for an ethno-theocratic one, seeking unity through a privileged identity at the expense of its African reality.

All these processes justify repression. As Dieste (2021) and Rhani *et al.* (2020) argue, framing Riffian demands as threats legitimises the use of force and denies the validity of

¹⁴ It originates from French encounters with the Kabyle of Algeria (Tilmatine, 2016). Not to mention that Arab nationalism spawned in response to French policies (Burke III, 1972; Brown, 1972).

grievances. The state's narrative hegemony ultimately amounts to narrative closure and ontological violence; the erasure of Riffian being, criminalising their existence and reducing identity to threat.

5.2.2. LANGUAGE AS BATTLEGROUND

Despite constitutional recognition in 2011, Tamazight remains unofficially marginalised in courts, hospitals, education, and media (CMA¹⁵, 2024; Gall, 2015), this mirrors Reyhner's (2010) model of cultural survival versus forced assimilation. Wyrzten (2013) highlights that even the choice of the rarely-used Tifinagh script was a political move: a declaration of indigenous legitimacy independent of Arab or colonial influence. Yet, linguistic justice remains hollow when exclusion persists.

The marginalisation of Tamazight mirrors colonial 'civilising' missions that framed indigenous tongues as 'barbarous dialects' (Crawford, 2007; Reyhner, 2010). Arabisation, tied to post-independence nationalism, elevated Arabic (or French) as the language of politics, education, and religion, while relegating Tamazight and Darija to backwardness and ignorance (Almasude, 2001; Loutfi, 2021). This linguistic hierarchy is not merely an act of prejudice, but a weapon of epistemic violence, severing oral traditions, limiting social mobility, and erasing non-Arab histories (El Guabli, 2021). If one's language is denied value, one's being denied recognition.

The devaluation of Tamazight as a dialect of the poor and uneducated is deliberate (Loutfi, 2021; Schwed, 2017). Even the historical prestige of Spanish in the Rif was eroded. For the same reasons, Darija is devalued, which, as Aune (2008) and Chtatou (1997) investigated, is akin to a pidgin of Arabic – it is too Amazigh, thus unwelcome.

Language, therefore, becomes the primary battleground of survival. The loss of Tamazight would weaken cultural memory and accelerate assimilation. Language is the expression of resistance and legitimacy. The loss of cultural memory due to the loss of oral transmission – as Tamazight is historically oral only – is why contemporary works such as El Idrissi's (2014) documentary on the Revolt and Akouh's (2025) book on the War and Abdelkrim

¹⁵ *Congrès Mondial Amazigh*.

5. ETHNOLINGUISTIC INJUSTICE
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are crucial. They record the unrecorded. This is the role of the diaspora, free of the yoke of censorship.

Language loss and linguisticism are strategic tools, not clumsy collateral of nationalism. Severing linguistic transmission allows the state to sever historical consciousness and weaken collective resistance.

6. TRANSFORMATION: TOWARDS EPISTEMIC PEACE

As demonstrated, the contradictions and symbolic closures that define the Riffian conflict do not disappear; they are managed, repressed, or hidden. What results is not peace, but negative peace – a fragile absence of violence *and* justice. True transformation demands more than stability. It requires the dismantling of structural, ontological, and epistemic violence itself; “*the master’s tools will never dismantle the master’s house*” (Lorde, 1979). This chapter outlines how PCC can guide such a transformation.

6.1. PEACE AS JUSTICE

Traditional models, such as Galtung’s TRANSCEND, treat contradiction as a static problem, a component, rather than a dynamically evolving root cause. They focus overwhelmingly on behavioural change (B) and material contradictions (C), while neglecting the deeper colonial structures (C) and epistemic erasures (A) that perpetuate injustice.

In postcolonial contexts, this oversight is fatal. Peace is mistakenly framed as an alternative to justice, rather than its expression. These methods perceive justice as an alternative, rival, or tool by which to achieve peace, rather than peace itself. Thereby, missing the presence of coloniality as the core contradiction. Consequently, interventions such as Morocco’s Equity and Reconciliation Commission (ERC), the 2011 constitutional reforms, and post-Hirak economic pledges manage surface behaviours without dismantling the epistemic and colonial logics underpinning and causing them. Hence, they have so far proven unfruitful.

The ERC has addressed Hassan’s abuses and their victims but never touched on the colonial structures it sustained and enabled, nor the epistemic closure (Slyomovics, 2001; 2005)¹⁶ – as per El Guabli (2020), “*a transitional justice process without perpetrators*” (p. 83). The constitutional reforms recognised Tamazight but have been unable to force its institutionalisation, as the Franco-Arabic hegemony in practice remains unbroken (Masbah, 2013; Loutfi, 2021). Similarly, post-Hirak promises have been delayed or unfulfilled, and the structural neglect persists (Debackere & Akouh, 2021).

¹⁶ Additionally, as per Grotti & Goldstein (2005), “*reports to the king*” and is not “*a court or a judicial body*” – its mandate and power is limited (p. 18).

The result is negative peace. Postcolonial justice reframes this by demanding structural, cultural, ontological, and narrative justice simultaneously. It demands transformation.

6.2. THREE ROUTES OF REDRESS

True transformation requires simultaneous interventions at the symbolic, structural, and systemic levels. The following routes offer a framework for postcolonial redress.

Narrative Redress targets **symbolic** violence by reopening suppressed histories and challenging national myths. Key measures could include:

- Publicly recognising Riffian resistance and its leaders as something to be celebrated as anticolonial, decolonial, and pan-African – Abdelkrim, Ameziane, the Hirak, and even beyond the Rif, figures like Ben Barka.
- Reinserting Amazighité in Moroccan identity, think national memory campaigns, adapting the national canon, and rejecting Arabism¹⁷.
- Issuing public apologies from the Moroccan state, and Spain, for historical atrocities – its actions during the Revolt, Riots, Hirak, Years of Lead, and even its inaction in response to the 2004 Al Hoceima earthquake, its invasion of Algeria, its occupation of the Western Sahara.

Narrative redress is not just symbolic but foundational. Without truth-telling, reconciliation remains impossible.

Structural Transformation tackles oppressive and neglectful **behaviours**, and thus indirectly Riffian dissent. Key interventions could include:

- Direct investment in Riffian infrastructure, education, healthcare, and the local economy.
- Affirmative, inclusive policies.
- Real protection and safeguards for cultural dissent, civil disobedience, and protests – constitutionally and judicially.

It removes the behavioural conditions that fuel cycles of dissent and repression and remains most similar to traditional methods. Gramsci (1999) reminds us that cultural hegemony is not

¹⁷ Arab supremacism, primarily on ethnolinguistic grounds.

just epistemic dominance, but a process of consent-making. Both narrative redress and structural transformation, then, constitute counter-hegemonic transformation, the elevation of suppressed epistemologies and cultural pluralism by de-normalising Arab-Islamic monoculturalism. Dismantling the hegemony is imperative for building Moroccan solidarity.

Cultural Redress is the most important and revolutionary of PCC, tackling the core **contradictions**. Interventions could include:

- Full institutionalisation of Tamazight. As an official language, it should be viable in courts, hospitals, administration, education, the job market, and media. Academics have affirmed the importance of primary education in one's native language (Nyika, 2015).
- The Rif should be completely demilitarised. The withdrawal of checkpoints and demilitarisation of the police, for one, but also unconditional pardons and reparations for direct victims, the Fikri family and Hirak protestors, such as the Zefzafi family.
- The state should accept and celebrate the plurality of its populace. One way of achieving that would be to provide regional autonomy and decentralisation, a federal monarchy, for instance. Culture needs political space to breathe.
- The fulfilment of Riffian demands. So, measures against corruption, the disempowering of the comprador class.

Morocco's rejection of coloniality must also extend beyond its borders and the Rif. Rebuilding Maghrebian ties with Algeria and Tunisia could serve not only as a diplomatic correction, but also as the symbolic restoration of the indigenous Amazigh realm severed by colonial cartography.

6.3. DARE TO INVENT: MOVING THE NEEDLE

All this is well and good, but it carries one main limitation: it places accountability on the state's doorstep. This raises a critical question: why would the state act? I consider three pathways: coercion, conviction, and compulsion.

First, coercion would be the levying of (political) force in order to pressure the domineering state into changing its behaviour. This has been successfully attempted in Morocco, during the reform period of late-Hassan II (1980s-1999), when foreign pressure

regarding human rights, particularly from Europe and the United States¹⁸, led to a liberalisation campaign (Willis, 2009), but also the (maligned) 2011 reforms in fear of ‘Arab’ Spring (Fernández Molina, 2011; Colin, 2024).

Diaspora communities live, largely, outside the censored, taboo culture of silence present in Morocco, particularly on topics like the Rif Revolt. This allows these communities to be more outspoken and reclaim their epistemology without the same (amount of) obstacles. Bouman (2020) affirms this, calling the Dutch Rif movement more radical than the Moroccan, proving that the diaspora – which by *jus sanguinis* citizenship laws are all considered Moroccan citizens – could easily escalate their activism, to potentially include their European governments, to levy high pressure on the makhzen.

Second, the state could be convinced. No, this is not naively appealing to their good nature but proving their potential benefit. A durable peace in Morocco could be economically fruitful, as a substantial proportion of the population is marginalised and therefore unable to partake in the economy – there is an untapped ‘consumer base.’ Moreover, human rights tend to be good marketing for the tourism industry, which a country as geographically varied and culinarily popular as Morocco could benefit from.

There is also the religious argument, which ought to convince the Sharifian¹⁹ monarchs – be that from conviction or communal pressure. The Qur’an commands justice even towards adversaries (Surah Al-Ma’idah, 5:8), while Islamic legal theory identifies the preservation of dignity, lineage, and intellect (read: epistemologies) as moral imperatives (Afridi, 2016).

Lastly, the state might be compelled in two ways: insurgency and intervention. Insurgency could initiate such a drastic change in the power dynamics that it might be convinced to join the negotiation table to find a compromise to retain as much power as possible. An intervention would be preferable, particularly from an internationally accredited body, through legal or political means.

Cases like the Basque appeals to the European Court of Human Rights or the Māori’s invocation of the Treaty of Waitangi²⁰ illustrate how marginalised, indigenous groups can

¹⁸ Though this does call into question the intentionality of such beyond economic liberalisation. Additionally, much of this pressure was internal, but in order to align with external expectations and standards (Willis, 2009).

¹⁹ Descendants of the Prophet Muhammed, which the Alawite dynasty is. In Islamic culture, these lineages hold special ‘noble’ status, privileges, and responsibilities.

²⁰ Although it has recently been called into question, as memorably protested by a haka in the New Zealand parliament (Corlett, 2025), illustrating the need to be vigilant.

weaponise legal frameworks to legitimise their claims (Tahana, 2025; Castells vs. Spain, 1992)²¹. The Riffians, and Imazighen as a whole, can do so by appealing to existing international agreements or statutes ratified by the Kingdom of Morocco, such as the ICCPR, ICESCR, or CERD²² (United Nations, n.d.; United Nations Geneva, 2023), to compel compliance.

Naturally, all three routes carry risks. As proven, coercion can provoke backlash. Similarly, conviction can be more easily co-opted and recycled into the comprador-machine than the 2011 demands were. Compulsion could also trigger a sense of victimhood, thus causing the state to lash out again or more harshly – the same epistemological scars colonialism left. Yet, all three – coercion, conviction, and compulsion – offer realistic pressure points for engaging a resistant hegemon without relying on naïve optimism nor outright revolution.

²¹ Especially the Castells case could be relevant legal precedent for Nasser Zefzafi and other Hirak protestors as it has been used in global cases and, interestingly, against Wilders for anti-Moroccan hate speech. Though not binding, it could prove persuasive at the UN level, e.g., the Human Rights Committee under ICCPR.

²² International Convention on Civil and Political Rights; International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights; Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination

7. CONCLUSION

So, how can a postcolonial conflictological approach explain the persistence of Riffian dissent and propose pathways toward ethnolinguistic justice?

Postcolonial conflictology (PCC) reframes the Riffian struggle as an inevitable product of deep, historically embedded (colonial) contradictions rather than spontaneous episodes of unrest. This begins by fusing Galtung's ABC-model with the 3S-dimensions, thereby critically expanding the architecture of conflict. This new triad (symbol-attitude, system-behaviour, structure-contradictions) is then theoretically grounded in postcolonial thought, allowing a layered diagnosis of protracted (postcolonial) conflicts.

Crucially, postcolonial theory offers not only the analytic tools but a decolonial ethos grounded in a philosophical peace-as-justice position.

This thesis also proposes a radical reorganisation of ABC. Primarily, contradictions are no simple component, they are the root, the origin, the conflict itself. Behaviour becomes the cyclical expression of that contradiction – a symptom. Lastly, what Galtung called 'attitude' is reframed as narrative – the symbolic terrain through which both contradictions and behaviours are legitimised, obscured, or mythologised – or: the 'means.' This includes national myths, racialised hierarchies, and dominant discourses.

Recognising the inadequacy of the traditional cycle, this thesis proposes a new model: the Conflict Helix (Figure 8). The Helix is composed of layered behaviour-loops, rooted in contradiction (C), justified by narrative (N), expressed through behaviour (B). Together they generate – or risk – entrenchment (E), the increasing difficulty of transformation as injustices calcify, historical memory fades, and victims and perpetrators pass.

Figure 8. The Conflict Helix

This new model reorients conflictology around coloniality, memory and ‘invisible’ violence (such as epistemic and symbolic); it represents an epistemic shift. Where traditional models like TRANSCEND treat structural issues as peripheral, static, or unavoidable, PCC centres coloniality as the generative force of protracted postcolonial conflicts. This allows us not only to explain conflict more fully but also to imagine its resolution: a structural, ontological, and epistemic transformation.

Ultimately, PCC demonstrates that peace without justice is fragile, especially in postcolonial conflicts. Stability is simply not enough; structural and ontological transformations make true reconciliation more than a pipedream. If postcolonial conflicts are born from erasure, then postcolonial peace *must* be built on remembrance, restoration, and celebration. The utility of PCC becomes clear when applied to the Riffian case.

If peace demands remembrance, restoration, and celebration, then Morocco offers a case of forgetfulness, marginalisation, and myth-making. In the Rif, and beyond, the aftershocks of colonialism were not resolved but absorbed, redirected, and redeployed. The absence of structural transformation after independence ended nothing; it merely turned conflict inward. What followed was no peace, but a colonial hand-me-down; a postcolony ruled in the coloniser’s image.

Thus, Morocco entered a new conflictual phase following independence, not one of domination, but of internal dominating and exclusion. The nationalist project, far from civic or inclusive, became a vehicle for Arab-Islamic homogenisation. This shift was avoidable; it was the result of elite consolidation and colonial continuity in a djellaba. Foreign domination was indeed removed, but the people’s soul remained appropriated, thereby I, and Amílcar Cabral²³, would argue that Morocco was never truly liberated; “*there’s a difference between peace and liberation, is there not?*” (Brook, 1968)²⁴.

This postcolonial nationalism operated through what Fanon (1963) might call the “*pitfall of national consciousness*,” a hollow mimicry of colonial structures with a new flag, although Morocco’s flag was unchanged. It elevated the Arab-Islamic identity to hegemonic status, displacing Morocco’s Amazigh, Sephardic, and multilingual realities (even more). The Rif, once a bastion of anti-imperial resistance, was rebranded as a rebellious periphery to be suppressed and excluded.

²³ I interpret Cabral’s 1970 speech *National Liberation and Culture* (2009).

²⁴ Quoting Kwame Ture (credited as Stokely Carmichael).

7. CONCLUSION

And yet, as Aïdi (2022) points out, reality opposes myth. The 2022 Moroccan national football team that flourished at the World Cup was an unintentional referendum on national identity. Darija, Tamazight, African pride, diaspora, and Islam coexisted without contradiction. The plural (true!) Morocco was not invented that Qatari winter, just broadcast to the world.

Riffian dissent is no rejection of Morocco, but a demand that Morocco be truer to itself. The contradiction lies not with the Rif, but within the nation – between its plural foundations and its exclusionary ideology, between its people and its elites. To break the cycle, Morocco must dismantle the myths that sustain it. What Riffians seek and sought is not secession but recognition of their pain, their pride, and their place in a plural Morocco. To quote Aimé Césaire²⁵ one last time, “*there’s room for all at the rendezvous of victory.*”

²⁵ Retrieved from Chopra (2012).

8. RECOMMENDATIONS

Academic

Firstly, this exercise has been a proof-of-concept, wherein I prove that a postcolonial framework is relevant, if not necessary, to properly analyse cases such as the Rif. Therein, I have recognised and reiterated that at this current stage, PCC is less actionable than the traditional method – while I will maintain that all models are inactionable, but theoretical, analytical, and context-dependent; models inform pathways of action. Therefore, I must suggest that future research be done to further establish PCC transformation methods, particularly regarding how justice would be demanded, as this is an idealistic area.

Secondly, I suggest the academic community expands PCC. Applying and expanding this framework and the Helix to other cases such as Cyprus, Kashmir, Palestine, Kurdistan, and the various indigenous movements in Canada and the United States.

Finally, the integration and solidification of PCC as a genuine, recognised branch of conflictology. One of the key achievements of this concept is how it challenges Western-centric paradigms and the monopoly of the United Nations in conflict resolution by proposing exactly the steps which they seem to consistently overlook. This foundational decolonial ethic is, as imparted by me, is imperative for any of its applicable cases and thus the framework.

Practical

For the case, Chapter 6, Transformation in Practice, constitutes a theoretical overview of what steps Morocco should take: cultural restoration, structural redress, and narrative redress. Through these transformations, Morocco can move beyond cycles of negative peace and finally dismantle the coloniality of its statehood, because a just Morocco would unravel the helix, not reinforce it.

What I will add is that Moroccan laws predating the 2011 constitutional reform should be approached with scepticism and considered for revision, echoing Mystal (2025). These laws were enacted before the formal recognition of Amazighité and thus lack the necessary safeguards of inclusion and democratic legitimacy. If Amazigh emancipation is to be taken seriously, legislative reform must be genuinely inclusive moving forward and in retrospect.

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APPENDIX – LIST OF KEY WORDS

Conflictology

- Conflict analysis
- Conflict resolution
- Conflict transformation
- J. Galtung
- Post-conflict Justice
- Reconciliation
- Transitional Justice

Postcolonial Theory

- A. Cabral
- A. Césaire
- A. Gramsci
- Coloniality
- Comprador
- E.W. Said
- Epistemic violence
- F. Fanon
- Imperialism
- Internal colonialism
- N. wa Thiong'o
- Neocolonialism
- Orientalism
- Postcolonial theory

Riffian case

- Abdelkrim
- Berber Dahir
- Berber Myth
- Bread Riots (Nador)
- Diaspora activism
- February 20 Movement (Arab Spring in Morocco)

TOWARD A POSTCOLONIAL CONFLICTOLOGY
RETHINKING THE RIFFIAN STRUGGLE

- Hirak Rif
- Reconciliation Morocco (ERC)
- Rif Rebellion/Revolt
- Rif War
- Riffian identity
- Years of Lead

Identity & Language

- Amazigh language (Tamazight)
- J. Reyhner (Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, AZ)
- Language discrimination
- Language revitalisation
- Language rights
- Linguistic resistance